

THE PROBLEM OF PERFORMANCE IN CELLO ART OF UZBEKISTAN

Mirmakhsudov Sherali Miraliyevich

Republican Specialized Music School named after R.Glier

Teacher of the cello class of the stringed instruments department

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11366851>

Abstract: This article provides detailed information about the appearance of the cello instrument, its formation, performance of the instrument, compositional works written for the cello voice, and the importance of the cello instrument in musical culture. Also, the introduction of cello performance into the music culture of Uzbekistan was explained.

Key words: Music art, Cello, musical instruments, range, composer's works, stringed instruments.

Introduction:

Cello (derived from the Italian word violoncello; short for cello) is a stringed and bowed musical instrument with four strings. In terms of the height of his voice, he is between the alto and the contrabass. Has an enlarged form of alt. Cello is a modern form of the ancient viola (Italian: viola da Gamba). The cello is tuned like the alto, but one octave lower. The volume of the cello is very large - three and a half octaves. A cellist plays with the cello upright between the knees, with the stem resting on the floor.

Cello is an indispensable instrument in ensembles and symphony orchestras. It is he who makes the sound technique of the tune deep, rich and perfect. Due to the melodiousness of its "voice", the cello is often played solo when a musical group needs to vividly express emotions such as melancholy, period or warm sadness, filling the melody with lyrical mood.

Violoncello is a stringed bow-type musical instrument from the bass and tenor registers. It has been known since the 16th century and visually resembles a viola or a violin, but is much larger in size. In music, the cello is used in the following areas due to its unlimited "sound" possibilities:

- solo (solo)
- in the orchestra,
- when the melody is performed by a string ensemble.

A cello, like a violin, has 4 strings. It is the lowest-pitched bowed string instrument, and some musical groups, such as a quartet or chamber ensemble, cannot function without it.

Cello strings are an octave lower than viola. The notes for his part are written in the tenor or bass-treble clef, but thanks to the unique playing

technique developed over the centuries of the cello's existence, its tonal range is very wide.

It is still not clear who invented the cello. The first mention of it appeared at the beginning of the 16th century, or rather, the first half, and they were associated with two masters of the production of stringed instruments - the Italian Gasparo da Salo and his namesake. student Paolo Maggini. There is another version about who and when the cello was invented. According to him, the creator of the instrument was the most famous craftsman of the Amati family in the 16th century named Andrea.

The historical, documented fact is that the modern form of the cello, with its typical string row and distinctive sound, is the work of Antonio Stradivari. In addition, famous musicians and masters such as Giuseppe Guarneri took part in the improvement of the instrument in different centuries. Carlo Bergonzi, Niccolo Amati, Domenico Montagnana and others. Since the end of the 18th century, the shape of the body, the dimensions of the instrument and its series of strings have not changed.

A violin bow or viola bow is not suitable for playing the cello. This indispensable attribute of the instrument consists of a reed made of natural bamboo or fernambuco wood, a black block with pearl inserts, natural or artificial horsehair. The tension of the horse on a cello bow is adjusted using an octagonal screw attached to the reed.

The capabilities of the cello, in terms of sound reproduction, differ from the capabilities of similar instruments in terms of width and depth. Masters of orchestral art describe his voice in this way

- melodious,
- slightly crushed,
- tense,
- watery.

In the palette of an ensemble, quartet or orchestra, the cello sounds like the lowest timbre of the human voice. During the solo performance of this instrument, the cello seems to be freely talking to the audience about something very important and real, its deep, melodious voice amazes not only art lovers, but also its listeners, literally hypnotizes. for the first time.

Each string of the cello sounds unique and unique, and their sound range extends from the juicy bass of men to the warm and soft viola characteristic of truly feminine parts. The world's greatest composers and musicians have

repeatedly noted that the cello, for example, is able to "tell" the plot of an opera without words or visual images.

The technique of playing the cello is fundamentally different from the technique of playing other stringed musical analogues. The tool is very large, even bulky, and it must be supported in three points - in the area of the spine (on the floor), closer to the right side of the chest and on the left knee. When learning to play the cello, the topics of the first lessons are how to tune it, how to hold it.

Next, master the skills of holding a bow. When the sound is released, the cello is turned slightly to the right of the musician so that it covers the instrument's strings completely. It is very important to ensure that the freedom of movement of the left hand is not limited by anything.

It's surprising that many beginning musicians, even with excellent hearing and the ability to play bowed instruments, cannot master the technique of playing the cello and stop at the stage of learning to hold and support it. .

The evaluation of the sound quality of cellos for the best musicians and musical groups with world-famous names is conducted in the dark, and in these original competitions, as a rule, models created by violin masters of the 16th, 17th and 18th centuries win.

Cello is not only a classical musical instrument. Finnish hard rock band Apocalyptica won't go on stage without him. Every tune of their songs includes a cello part, and this kind of rock sounds very beautiful, original, but traditional for the genre. The instrument is used not only as a musical instrument - the artist Julia Borden paints abstract paintings on the body of the cello, which are actively bought by art lovers around the world and decorate the richest homes and even museums.

The cello is used as a string quartet or chamber and symphony orchestra instrument, and is often a very versatile and important solo instrument. Cello music dates from the Baroque to the present day and has always been very popular. Initially, this type of instrument was used for supporting parts called "bass parts", later it took one of the main places among solo instruments. This was due to the great cellists who inspired composers to expand their repertoire and create new works specifically for it.

The first solo works for the cello are the compositions of Domenico Gabrielli, which are widely used by cellists and are popular among fans of this instrument. Among the earliest works currently being performed are the six important works for solo cello by Johann Sebastian Bach. It is worth noting once

again that in Baroque music, the cello was usually the instrument that implemented the harmonic basis, that is, "basso continuo". In the second half of the 18th century, it gradually became an independent instrument, replacing the alto da gamba, which surpassed it in terms of technical and expressive capabilities. The virtuoso of this instrument, Luigi Boccherini, contributed to the development and popularization of the cello.

Its popularity was also due to the fact that many aristocrats played these instruments. The most famous of them was Frederick William II of Prussia. In those days, only men played the cello. But at the beginning of the twentieth century, women cellists began to master this instrument. Initially, they held the cello not as it is today, but on the side, that is, between the legs.

Concertos for cello and orchestra were created in the 19th and 20th centuries, including Robert Schumann, Camille Saint-Saëns, Dvorak. Pyotr Tchaikovsky's famous "Variations on a Rococo Theme" and his works for small groups of instruments gained worldwide fame. Excellent performers became a source of inspiration for composers who significantly expanded the relatively modest solo repertoire of the instrument.

Mstislav Rostropovich had special merits in the evolution of the cello. This virtuoso musician and great teacher nurtured several generations of soloists who cemented the cello's status as a solo instrument alongside the piano and violin. The oldest surviving cellos are two cellos made by Andrea Amati between 1560 and 1570.

Popular works for cello.

J. S. Bach - Suite 1 in G Major (listen).

P. I. Tchaikovsky. - Variations on a Rococo theme for cello and orchestra (listen).

A. Dvorak - concerto for cello and orchestra (listen).

C. Saint-Saens - "Swan" (listen).

I. Brahms - Double Concerto for Violin and Cello (listen).

Cello is also very popular in Uzbekistan. Cello performance in our country was formed at the end of the 19th century. Among the composers of Uzbekistan, S. Jalil wrote a concerto for cello and orchestra, G. Mushel, B. Giyenko, F. YanovYanovsky, S. Karimkhojayev, N. Zakirov wrote various pieces for cello. It is worth noting that I have connected my scientific research topic with the Violoncello musical instrument. Because the cello instrument gives spiritual nourishment to a person, elevates the world of imagination.

References:

1. Easton CDPJ (2000) A Biography. New York: Da Capo Press,.

2. Eislser E (2001) "The Versatility of Yo-Yo Ma." Strings Mag., 94: 47-54.
3. Faber T (2006). Stradivari's Genius: Five Violins, One Cello, and Three Centuries of Enduring Perfection. New York: Random House. Hargrave R (2001).
4. Ibragimov, B. (2023). Types And Importance Of Innovative Technologies In Education. Молодые ученые, 1(20), 96-98.
5. Hillard K (2008). "History of the cello". 2002. Essortment. .
6. Howards K (2008). Personal Interview.
7. Janof T (1996) "Cello Technique Made Simple". The Strad Magazine. 3 Feb.